

INTEGRATION OF COMPUTER-BASED LANGUAGE LEARNING INTO CLASSROOM ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: *The article reveals the features of using computer technologies in foreign language teaching. The main focus is on the theoretical and practical use of information technology and the advantages of this approach for learning English in independent work of students.*

Keywords: *interactive ways, psychological aspects, pedagogical aspects, modern information technologies, audio animations, video animations, electronic textbooks, multimedia products, computer training systems, multimedia and educational programs, multimedia presentations, extracurricular activities information technologies, ICT.*

Introduction

Today's society is rapidly developing due to the emergence of modern information technologies. Nowadays, the use of computer technologies and its new possibilities in teaching is of great importance. It helps teachers to find different ways to improve the quality of teaching. For example, in the modern teaching process, the project methodology of teaching foreign languages and Internet resources are aimed at the individualization of teaching, taking into account the skills, level of education and interests of young people. In addition, it should be noted that the role of teachers is to create a supportive classroom environment in which they constantly decide, guide, explain, connect the old with the new, recognize nonverbal communication, and provide moral support.

Materials and methods

Achieving positive results in education is determined, first of all, by the effective organization of educational and educational work to teach the young generation the basics of scientific knowledge, to expand the scope of their worldview and thinking, and to form their spiritual and moral qualities. In this regard, many changes are being made to the educational process, new approaches are being implemented. One of them is to increase the efficiency of classes using information and communication technologies. Based on this, the introduction of information and communication

technologies into the educational process is the demand of the time. One of the important tasks of today's pedagogy is to increase students' interest in subjects, to develop their mental and creative thinking, intellectual abilities, to ensure interdisciplinary connection. It is a priority to organize classes based on advanced pedagogical technologies, to teach students to work independently, to use the possibilities of information technologies wisely, and to improve the quality of mastering the taught subject. In this regard, different methods are used in the teaching of primary education. One of them is the use of modern information technologies. The rapid development of modern information technologies, their rapid penetration into the field of education, and the fact that they are becoming important in our lives, require the appropriate formation of our knowledge and skills in this regard. Therefore, it was recommended to teach using computers in elementary grades.

Content and methods of interactive education in the conditions of cooperative education Implementation of interactive educational technologies in the process of cooperative education includes the use of interactive educational methods (students to analyze life situations, make their own decisions, teaching self-defense and respect). The perspective of others they have the necessary communication skills in a relaxed environment) from a collaborative perspective on foreign language learning using technology¹.

Electronic textbooks, manuals and presentations created for primary school students are widely used in the educational process. In the teaching of reading, mother tongue, mathematics and natural sciences, with the help of information technologies, various demonstration slides can be used in lesson processes. For example: in the subjects of reading and mother tongue, reading letters and words together on a big screen, then reading small fairy tales and stories, writing letters correctly and beautifully; solving problems using simple operations in mathematics, using slides, organizing various calculation games; understanding of natural phenomena can be given using simple slides.

Interest is responsible for a personal way of engaging in activities that direct students to a specific, selected response to existing conditions².

¹ I. Aldashev The importance of using modern methods in teaching russian as a foreign language. "Экономика и социум" №11(78) 2020 www.iupr.ru

² S. Jabborova. The problem of increasing the interest of students in the Russian language at the university "Economics and Society" No. 12 (79) 2020 www.iupr.ru

The use of these methods motivates the development of oral speech of a young and knowledge-hungry student, increases the skills of oral calculation, creativity, research and thinking skills¹.

The use of electronic presentations as demonstration and demonstration material in the lesson will greatly help the teacher. Providing educational material in the form of animations in an electronic presentation makes it easier to understand the subject and increases visibility. Demonstration slides can also be given to students as handouts. An example of this is the electronic presentation on the topic "Agreements" created for use in 4th grade mother tongue classes. The electronic textbook can be used for independent education and effective assimilation of educational materials. In the electronic textbook, the teaching materials of the subject are provided to the student in interactive ways, psychological and pedagogical aspects, modern information technologies, audio and video animations are appropriately used. Book.uz site has electronic textbooks of almost all subjects for students of grades 1-4. But they are not presented in the form of text and sound. It is advisable to provide electronic textbooks in the form of text and audio, in the form of a slide show. The combined use of audio and video information dramatically increases the effectiveness of teaching.

In the context of multimedia, learning can be made more effective by engaging all types of the learner's sensory perception and arming the intellect with new conceptual tools².

Today's teacher is required to be able to use information technologies in the course of the lesson, to teach students to freely use a computer, to acquire modern knowledge thoroughly, and to become mature individuals.

Discussion and results

As well as, if we discuss about using information and communication technologies, we will divide into five main directions in foreign language lessons can be distinguished:

1. Use of multimedia products and computer training systems. This direction is mainly typical of the field of teaching foreign languages with the help of ICT. There are many programs for learning a foreign language, all of which use ready-made computer training courses with phonetic, grammatical and lexical material consolidation exercises. Educational materials in such programs often consist of two parts: theoretical and practical, and the training is based on interactive exercises on

¹ M. Ch. Aliyev. "Information technologies" study guide (in Uzbek and Russian languages). T.: UzDJTU 2018.

² I. Aldashev. To use the specific properties of the computer, allowing to individualize the educational process and turn to fundamentally new cognitive means. "Economy and society" №6(73) 2020 www.iupr.ru

various aspects of the foreign language. It is recommended to use computer training programs at all levels.

2. Creation of multimedia and educational programs. The computer allows us to use and deliver a large amount of educational information: various texts, exercises, audio and multimedia information. In addition, it can be supplemented, changed or given in a new form. However, in order to fully use all these possibilities, it is necessary to create a computer training program. All components of the computer-based training program should, first of all, correspond to the goals of teaching a foreign language.

3. Creating multimedia presentations. Often, teachers claim that it is very difficult to find the necessary visual material for the lesson. To solve this problem, teachers create their own presentations on the topics they need. Using presentations in the classroom is a very effective way to have a positive impact on students. Tables, animations, video and audio recordings can be created and placed in the presentation. New vocabulary can be well explained with photos and pictures, fixation of new material is done with the help of pre-prepared exercises.

4. Use of ICT in extracurricular activities. Currently, ICT is widely used not only for traditional classes, but also for conducting extracurricular activities with students. When working on educational projects, students refer to various sources of information: electronic encyclopedias, Internet search engines. Students use text and image editors, and present their work using presentations, photos, or videos.

5. Use of Internet resources. The Internet is a global international network that allows you to search for necessary information and use information from various information sources. There are many e-learning programs for learning a foreign language. In the process of teaching a foreign language, the use of relevant information via e-mail is also very popular.

Multimedia technologies allow listening to speech in a foreign language, which also allows you to separate words into words and compare the pronunciation and spelling of words. It is also possible to record the student's spoken word or phrase for later review and correction. Using multimedia technology, sound cards allow users to record their speech and then compare it with the pronunciation of other speakers. The graphics capabilities of computers can represent any type of activity in the form of pictures or animations. This is especially important when learning new vocabulary. Using ICT in grammar lessons is very useful in learning any subject. Properly placed material, successfully used color design, the use of tables and charts will help teachers to conduct their lessons in a more interesting and colorful way. In addition, it can be more interesting to manage the level of grammar skills learned with the help of ICT.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the introduction of information and communication technologies has become an important direction in learning foreign languages. Power Point presentation, e-mail correspondence, educational programs on CD-ROM, Internet resources in teaching foreign languages help students to develop language and communicative competences, increase interest in independent learning activities.

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